

First Data on Dolichopodidae (Diptera) of Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Region of Russia

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Grichanov I. Ya. First data on Dolichopodidae (Diptera) of Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Region of Russia. Summary. The faunistic data of the results of collecting dolichopodids (32 species) in the Khantia-Mansia in July-August, 2010 are presented. All species are recorded from the Region for the first time.

Key words: Diptera, Dolichopodidae, fauna, Russia, Khantia-Mansia.

Гричанов И. Я. Первые данные о Dolichopodidae (Diptera) Ханты-Мансийского автономного округа, Россия. Резюме. Представлены результаты сборов долихоподид (32 вида) в Ханты-Мансийском автономном округе России в июле-августе 2010 г. Все виды впервые отмечаются для округа.

Ключевые слова: Diptera, Dolichopodidae, фауна, Россия, Ханты-Мансийский автономный округ.

Гричанов І. Я. Перші відомості про Dolichopodidae (Diptera) Ханті-Мансійського автономного округу, Росія. Резюме. Наведено результати зборів доліхоподид (32 вида) в Ханті-Мансійському автономному окрузі Росії у липні-серпні 2010 р. Всі види вперше відмічено для округу.

Ключові слова: Diptera, Dolichopodidae, фауна, Росія, Ханті-Мансійський автономний округ.

Introduction

The Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Region (=Okrug) or Khantia-Mansia or Ugra is one of the largest Regions in West Siberia (534,800 km²). The basic part of the territory is occupied by swamped taiga. When studying recent Diptera catalogs, I have found that the fauna of the long-legged flies (Dolichopodidae) of Khantia-Mansia remained virtually unstudied (Гричанов и Негроров, 1979; Negrobov, 1991; Grichanov, 2003–2010). The only reliable record of one species, *Hercostomus fugax* (Loew, 1857), is mentioned from the territory of the Region adjacent to the Urals, i.e., from the Shchekur'ya River valley (Малоземов и др., 1997). This paper presents the new records in detail. Most species are widespread across the Palearctic Region or even across the Holarctic Realm, being often recorded in the neighboring territories. The *Chrysotus caerulescens* Negrobov and *Medetera sibirica* Negrobov first finds after description and the easternmost finds of *Argyra spoliata* Kowarz, *Dolichopus acuticornis* Wiedemann and *Medetera senicula* Kowarz also deserve noting. Collecting of the sister species *Rhaphium crassipes* (Meigen) and *R. latimanum* Kahanpää (or phenotypes of the same species?) by the same water trap is also interesting.

Material and Methods

A hand net and yellow water traps were used for collecting. During the collecting trip to the Khantia-Mansia in July-August, 2010, 32 species were found in this territory

by Konstantin Tomkovich (the Zoological Museum of Moscow State University). Mainly wet localities (except tree trunks *Medetera* species were taken from) were explored. The collector of all specimens is Konstantin Tomkovich; his name and the name of the collecting Region are omitted. Specimens examined in this study are deposited in the above-mentioned Museum. The species are illustrated with Zeiss Discovery V-12 stereomicroscope and AxioCam MRc5 camera. General distribution of species is given after Negrobov (1991) and Grichanov (2003–2010).

New records

Argyra spoliata Kowarz, 1879

Material examined. E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.77°N, 59.71°E, 9–11.VII.2010, 1 ♂; E Ural, 622 m asl., 63.818°N, 59.562°E, 6–8.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, Finland, Norway, Romania, Russia (Leningrad, Khantia-Mansia), Sweden. Type locality: Czech: «bei Marienbad in Bohmen» [= Mariánské Lázně].

Campicnemus scambus (Fallén, 1823)

Material examined. Mukhino, 60.89°N, 68.70°E, 7–13.VIII.2010, 1 ♂; E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.766°N, 59.716°E, 1–4.VII.2010, 1 ♂; Riv. It'yakh, 61.85°N, 69.06°E, 22.VII.2010, 1 ♀; Shapsha env., near river, 30 m asl., 61.087°N, 69.442°E, 14–16.VII.2010, 1 ♂; Shapsha env., forest, 30 m asl., 61.087°N, 69.442°E, 15–16.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia,

Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (Arkhangelsk, Bashkiria, Chelyabinsk, Karelia, Krasnodar, Leningrad, Moscow, Murmansk, Nenetsia, Pskov, Ryazan', Saratov, Ekaterinburg, Tver', Altai, Irkutsk, Khantia-Mansia, Krasnoyarsk, Khabarovsk, Vladivostok, Yamal, S Kamchatka), Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, UK, Ukraine (Kherson, Odessa). Type locality: Sweden: Esperod.

Chrysotus aff. *baicalensis* Negrobov et Maslova, 1995

Material examined. E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.77°N, 59.71°E, 9–11.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Russia (Irkutsk, ?Khantia-Mansia). Type locality: Russia: Irkutsk Region, Listvenichnoe.

Chrysotus caerulescens Negrobov, 1980

Material examined. E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.77°N, 59.71°E, 9–11.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Mongolia, Russia (Altai, Buryatia, Khantia-Mansia, Krasnoyarsk, Yakutia, Yamalia). Type locality: Russia: Sob' river, Bol'shoi Ural, Obdorsk [= Salekhard].

Chrysotus viridifemoratus von Roser, 1840 (Fig. 1)

Material examined. E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.766°N, 59.716°E, 1–4.VII.2010, 14 ♂ ♀.

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Romania; Russia (Khantia-Mansia, Krasnoyarsk, Novosibirsk, Yakutia, Yamalia), Slovakia, Switzerland, UK, Ukraine (Carpathiens, Chernovtsy). Type locality: not given [Germany: Württemberg].

Fig. 1. *Chrysotus viridifemoratus* von Roser, male

Dolichopus acuticornis Wiedemann, 1817 (Fig. 2)

Material examined. Riv. Lyamin bridge env., 75 m asl., 61.73°N, 71.03°E, 21.VII.2010, 3 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia, N Kazakhstan, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia (Leningrad, Moscow, Pskov, Voronezh, "Ural", Khantia-Mansia), Romania, Slovakia, Sweden, UK, Ukraine (Cherkasy, Ternopil). Type locality: Germany: Holstein.

Fig. 2. *Dolichopus acuticornis* Wiedemann, male head

Dolichopus annulipes Zetterstedt, 1838

Material examined. E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.77°N, 59.71°E, 9–11.VII.2010, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; E Ural, 622 m asl., 63.818°N, 59.562°E, 6–8.VII.2010, 1 ♂; Lake, 77 asl., 62.66°N, 71.95°E, 24–26.VII.2010, 1 ♀; Seliyarovo env., 50 m asl., 61.467°N, 70.731°E, 17–20.VII.2010, 1 ♂, 1 ♀.

Distribution. Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Latvia, Norway, Russia ("Caucasus", Arkhangelsk, Karelia, Komi, Leningrad, Murmansk, Buryatia, Khantia-Mansia, Magadan, Primorskii Terr., Yakutia, Yamalia), Sweden; Nearctic: Canada and USA: Alaska, Yukon, British Columbia, Ontario to Newfoundland (Labrador), south to New York. Type locality: Sweden: «Lapponia Umensi; Lycksele; Lapponia Dalekarlia».

Dolichopus brevipennis Meigen, 1824

Material examined. Shapsha env., near river, 30 m asl., 61.087°N, 69.442°E, 14–16.VII.2010, 3 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belarus, Belgium, China (Xinjiang), Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, N Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia (Adygea, Arkhangelsk, Baskortostan, Kabardino-Balkaria, Karelia, Krasnodar, Kirov, Komi, Leningrad, Moscow, Murmansk, Novgorod, Perm, Pskov, Ryazan, Voronezh, Yaroslavl; Altai, Cis-Baikalia, Khantia-Mansia, Yakutia), Sweden, UK; Nearctic: Canada and USA: Alaska, Yukon, British Columbia, Northwest Terr., Montana, Alberta, Saskatchewan, Quebec, Prince Edward Is, Newfoundland (Labrador). T; Nearctic: ype locality: Sweden.

Dolichopus discifer Stannius, 1831

Material examined. Riv. Vats'yavin, 62.695°N, 72.046°E, 25.VII.2010, 1 ♂; E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.766°N, 59.716°E, 1–4.VII.2010, 3 ♂; E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.77°N, 59.71°E, 9–11.VII.2010, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; Riv. Soromlorop'yavin, 77 m asl., 62.650°N, 71.891°E, 26.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Belarus; Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, N Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania; Russia (Karelia, Komi, Leningrad, Moscow, Murmansk, Novgorod, Vologda, Altai, Baikal, Khantia-Mansia, Khabarovsk, Sakhalin, Primorskii Terr.), Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, UK, Ukraine (Kharkiv); Nearctic: Canada and USA: Alaska, British Columbia to Quebec and Nova Scotia, southward to Colorado and New York. Type locality: Germany.

***Dolichopus lepidus* Staeger, 1842**

Material examined. Riv. It'yakh, 61.85°N, 69.06°E, 22.VII.2010, 3 ♂; E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.77°N, 59.71°E, 9–11.VII.2010, 1 ♂; Shapsha env., near river, 30 m asl., 61.087°N, 69.442°E, 14–16.VII.2010, 2 ♂; Lake, 77 asl., 62.66°N, 71.95°E, 24–26.VII.2010, 1 ♂; Riv. Vats'yavin, 62.695°N, 72.046°E, 25.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belarus, Belgium, ?Bosnia and Herzegovina, China (Shaanxi, Beijing), ?Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Georgia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan, Latvia, ?Macedonia, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (Karelia, Krasnodar, Leningrad, Moscow, Murmansk, Novgorod, Pskov, Voronezh, Khantia-Mansia, Primorskii Terr.), Slovakia, ?Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, UK, ?Yugoslavia; Oriental: China. Type locality: Denmark: «Leersoens i Slutningen» [Lersøen nearby Copenhagen].

***Dolichopus linearis* Meigen, 1824**

Material examined. Shapsha env., near river, 30 m asl., 61.087°N, 69.442°E, 14–16.VII.2010, 2 ♂; Mukhino, 60.89°N, 68.70°E, 7–13.VIII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, China (Heilongjiang, Jilin, Beijing, Inner Mongolia, Gansu, Xinjiang, Qinghai), Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania; Russia (Adygea, Krasnodar, Leningrad, Novgorod, Pskov, Voronezh, Baikal, Khantia-Mansia, Primorskii Terr.), Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, UK. Type locality: not given.

***Dolichopus mannerheimi* Zetterstedt, 1838**

Material examined. E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.77°N, 59.71°E, 9–11.VII.2010, 2 ♂; E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.766°N, 59.716°E, 1–4.VII.2010, 1 ♂, 1 ♀.

Distribution. Finland, Mongolia, Norway, Russia (Karelia, Murmansk, Altai, Buryatia, Irkutsk, Kamchatka, Khabarovsk Terr., Khantia-Mansia, Magadan), Sweden, China (Xinjiang, Heilongjiang); Nearctic: Alaska, Yukon. Type locality: Sweden: «Lapponia Umensis, Stensele; Trensunda; Naestansjö; in parocia Wilhelmina».

***Dolichopus nitidus* Fallén, 1823**

Material examined. Riv. Vats'yavin, 62.695°N, 72.046°E, 25.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, "Palestine", Poland, Romania, Russia (Karelia, Krasnodar, Leningrad, Lipetsk, Moscow, Novgorod, Voronezh, Khantia-Mansia, Tomsk, Primorskii Terr.), Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, UK, Ukraine (Kharkiv, Odessa, Ternopil); Oriental: China (Henan, Shanghai). Type locality: not given.

***Dolichopus plumipes* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Material examined. Shapsha env., near river, 30 m asl., 61.087°N, 69.442°E, 14–16.VII.2010, 2 ♂; Mukhino, 60.89°N, 68.70°E, 7–13.VIII.2010, 1 ♂; Lake, 77 asl., 62.66°N, 71.95°E, 24–26.VII.2010, 1 ♂; 73 m asl., 62.10°N, 71.035°E, 29–30.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Khantia-Mansia; throughout Palaearctic and Nearctic Regions; Mexico; Oriental: China, India (Kashmir). Type locality: Slovenija: «Carnioliae indigena».

***Dolichopus remipes* Wahlberg, 1839**

Material examined. Riv. It'yakh, 61.85°N, 69.06°E, 22.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Belarus, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Latvia, Norway, Poland, Russia (Karelia, Leningrad, Khantia-Mansia, Buryatia, Yakutia, S

Kamchatka), Sweden; Nearctic: Canada and USA: Washington, Alberta; Saskatchewan, Manitoba, Ontario, Quebec, Nova Scotia, Maine, Montana, Minnesota, Wisconsin. Type locality: Sweden: Gusum.

***Dolichopus unguilatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. Shapsha env., near river, 30 m asl., 61.087°N, 69.442°E, 14–16.VII.2010, 4 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belarus, Belgium, ?Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, China (Xinjiang), Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, England, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, ?Macedonia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania; Russia (Karelia, Leningrad, Novgorod, Pskov, Volodga; Adygea, Alania, Kabardino-Balkaria, Karachai-Cherkessia, Krasnodar, Kursk, Lipetsk, Moscow, Orenburg, Perm, Tatarstan, Voronezh, Altai, Khantia-Mansia, Khabarovsk); Slovakia, ?Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Kharkiv, Kiev, Odessa, Ternopil, Carpathia), ?»Yugoslavia». Type locality: Europe.

***Dolichopus urbanus* Meigen, 1824**

Material examined. E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.77°N, 59.71°E, 9–11.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia (Arkhangelsk, Karelia, Leningrad, Moscow, Murmansk, Voronezh, Kabardino-Balkaria, Karachai-Cherkessia, Krasnodar, S Ural, Khantia-Mansia, Buryatia), Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, UK. Type locality: not given.

***Dolichopus zetterstedti* Stenhammar, 1851 (Fig. 3)**

Material examined. Riv. Vats'yavin, 62.695°N, 72.046°E, 25.VII.2010, 3 ♂.

Distribution. Finland, N Kazakhstan, Norway, Russia (Karelia, Leningrad, Murmansk, Khantia-Mansia, Yakutia, Yamalia), Sweden. Type locality: Sweden: Ringstad.

Fig. 3. *Dolichopus zetterstedti* Stenhammar, mal

***Gymnopternus aerosus* (Fallén, 1823)**

Material examined. Lake, 77 asl., 62.66°N, 71.95°E, 24–26.VII.2010, 1 ♂; Riv. Soromlorop'yavin, 77 m asl., 62.650°N, 71.891°E, 26.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Abkhazia, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland,

Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Lithuania, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (Adygea, Alania, Karelia, Karachai-Cherkessia, Krasnodar, Leningrad, Lipetsk, Moscow, Murmansk, Novgorod, Pskov, Voronezh, «Ural», Buryatia, Khantia-Mansia, Primorskii Terr.), Slovakia, Sweden, Tajikistan, UK, Ukraine (Chernovtsy, Kherson, Odessa, Uzhhorod); Oriental: Taiwan. Type locality: not given [Sweden].

Gymnopternus brevicornis (Loew, 1857)

Material examined. Riv. Lyamin bridge env., 75 m asl., 61.73°N, 71.03°E, 21.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (Karelia, Leningrad, Murmansk, Voronezh, «Ural», Altai, Khantia-Mansia, Primorskii Terr.), Sweden, Switzerland, UK, Ukraine (Carpathians, Odessa). Type locality: not given [Denmark].

Medetera senicula Kowarz, 1877

Material examined. Seliyarovo env., 50 m asl., 61.467°N, 70.731°E, 17–20.VII.2010, 2 ♀.

Distribution. Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Poland, Russia (Karelia, Leningrad, Khantia-Mansia), Sweden, UK. Type locality: Poland: «Südwestliche Polen».

Medetera sibirica Negrobov, 1972 (Figs. 4–5)

Material examined. Riv. It'yakh, 61.85°N, 69.06°E, 22.VII.2010, 1 ♂; Lake, 77 asl., 62.66°N, 71.95°E, 24–26.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. E Russia: Khantia-Mansia, Novosibirsk. Type locality: Russia: «Sibirien, Geb. Novosibirsk, Distr. Togutshinski, Koyrak».

Fig. 4. *Medetera sibirica* Negrobov, male habitus

Fig. 5. *Medetera sibirica* Negrobov, male wing

Remark. The specimen examined is the closest to *M. sibirica* by habitus and genital morphology as described by Negrobov, Stackelberg (1974), differing in pale rather than black proepimeral setae.

Medetera signaticornis Loew, 1857

Material examined. E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.766°N, 59.716°E, 1–4.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Mongolia, Norway, Poland, Russia (Arkhangel'sk, Krasnodar, Leningrad, Murmansk, Novosibirsk, Perm', Voronezh, Middle Volga, Khantia-Mansia, Primorskii Terr., Tuva), Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Crimea, Carpathia); Nearctic: Canada and USA: Alaska, Yukon, Northwest Terr., British Columbia, Washington, Oregon, Idaho, Alberta, Wyoming, Manitoba, Ontario, Michigan, Indiana, Quebec, New York, Pennsylvania, New Brunswick, Maine, Prince Edward Is. Type locality: ?Germany.

Medetera veles Loew, 1861

Material examined. Shapsha env., near river, 30 m asl., 61.087°N, 69.442°E, 14–16.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Belgium, Czech Republic, Finland, Kazakhstan, Norway, Russia (Arkhangel'sk, Karelia, Leningrad, Lipetsk, Murmansk, Perm', Voronezh, Khantia-Mansia, Primorskii Terr., Yakutia), Sweden, UK; Oriental: Japan (Ryukyu); Nearctic: throughout Canada and USA, Bermuda, Mexico; Neotropical: Mexico. Type locality: USA: Florida.

Neurigona pallida (Fallén, 1823)

Material examined. Near river Baybalakovskaya, 60.97°N, 68.62°E, 6.VIII.2010, 1 ♂; Mukhino, 60.89°N, 68.70°E, 7–13.VIII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania; S Russia (Karelia, Karachai-Cherkessia, Leningrad, Lipetsk, Moscow, Orenburg, Voronezh, Khantia-Mansia, Tomsk), Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, UK, Ukraine (Crimea, Kharkiv). Type locality: Sweden: Scania [= Skane].

Rhaphium crassipes (Meigen, 1824)

Material examined. E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.77°N, 59.71°E, 9–11.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (Arkhangelsk, Karelia, Leningrad, Lipetsk, Moscow, Murmansk, Nenetsia, Voronezh, Adygea, Alania, Karachai-Cherkessia, Krasnodar, Baikal, Irkutsk, Kamchatka, Khantia-Mansia, Krasnoyarsk, Primorskii Terr., Yamalia), Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, UK; Nearctic: Canada: Yukon Terr., Northwest Terr., British Columbia, Alberta to Quebec; USA: Alaska. Type locality: not given.

Rhaphium dichromum Negrobov, 1976

Material examined. E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.77°N, 59.71°E, 9–11.VII.2010, 2 ♂.

Distribution. Russia (Murmansk, Altai, Buryatia, Khantia-Mansia, Magadan). Type locality: Russia: Buryatskaya ASSR, Barguzinskii Reserve.

Rhaphium elegantulum (Meigen, 1824)

Material examined. Riv. It'yakh, 61.85°N, 69.06°E, 22.VII.2010, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; Shapsha env., near river, 30 m asl., 61.087°N, 69.442°E, 14–16.VII.2010, 4 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Latvia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (Karelia, Krasnodar, Leningrad, Murmansk, Voronezh, «Polar Ural», «Igarka», Baikal, Kamchatka, Khantia-Mansia, Krasnoyarsk), Spain, Sweden, UK; Nearctic: USA and Canada: Alaska, Oregon, Idaho, Colorado, Quebec to Nova Scotia and New Brunswick, southward to New York and New Hampshire. Type locality: Germany: Hamburg.

Rhaphium glaciale (Ringdahl, 1920) (Fig. 6)

Material examined. E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.77°N, 59.71°E, 9–11.VII.2010, 1 ♂; Riv. It'yakh, 61.85°N, 69.06°E, 22.VII.2010, 4 ♂; E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.766°N, 59.716°E, 1–4.VII.2010, 2 ♂, 1 ♀.

Distribution. Finland, Norway, Russia (Murmansk, Baikal, Khantia-Mansia, Krasnoyarsk, Magadan, Yakutia), Sweden; Nearctic: «North America». Type locality: Sweden: Lappland, nr Torneträsk; Jämtland, Wällista.

Fig. 6. *Rhaphium glaciale* (Ringdahl), male

Rhaphium latimanum Kahanpää, 2007

Material examined. E Ural, 256 m asl., 63.77°N, 59.71°E, 9–11.VII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Finland, Russia (Khantia-Mansia, Yamalia, Yakutia, Magadan). Type locality: Finland: Kilpisjärvi.

Rhaphium umbripenne (Frey, 1915) (Fig. 7)

Material examined. Mukhino, 60.89°N, 68.70°E, 7–13.VIII.2010, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Finland, Norway, Russia (Karelia, Leningrad, Murmansk, Kamchatka, Khantia-Mansia), Sweden; Nearctic: «North America». Type locality: Finland: Mäntsälä, Metsäpirtti, Paadama, Yläne, Tavastehus, Kuopio, Tuovilanlahti, Ilomantsi, Jacobstad, Säräisniemi, Kuusamo, Muonio, Enontekis, Kantalaks, Ponoj, Fl. Voronje; Russia: Kola Peninsula.

Fig. 7. *Rhaphium umbripenne* (Frey), male

Thrypticus intercedens Negrobov, 1967 (Fig. 8)

Material examined. Shapsha env., near river, 30 m asl., 61.087°N, 69.442°E, 14–16.VII.2010, 2 ♂.

Fig. 8. *Thrypticus intercedens* Negrobov, male

Distribution. Finland, France, Germany, Iran [Negrobov, 1991], Norway, Russia (Yaroslavl, Khantia-Mansia, Sayan Mnts., Yakutia), Sweden. Type locality: Russia: Borok, Jaroslavl' Region.

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